

Small-angle X-ray scattering of single-wall carbon nanotubes dispersed in molten poly(ethylene terephthalate)

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1. Introduction

The extraordinary mechanical properties of single-wall carbon nanotubes (SWCNT) make them suitable additives for a new generation of polymer nanocomposites¹. In particular the combination of a high aspect ratio with tube diameters in the range of a few of nanometers provide SWCNT-based nanocomposites with specific properties differing from those achieved in classical composites^{1,2}. However, mechanical properties of SWCNT nanocomposites, for example Young Modulus, are still very far from the theoretical value of SWCNT (~ 1 TPa)^{3,4}. In order to transfer the outstanding properties of SWCNT to the composite material one essential and difficult step involves the fine dispersion of the nanotubes within the polymer matrix^{5,6}. Microscopy techniques, like Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) or Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), are very useful to reveal the presence of individual nanotubes in the nanocomposite⁴. Small-angle scattering techniques can be useful to evaluate the average dispersion of SWCNT^{5,6}. Recently small-angle scattering measurements, both with neutrons or with X-rays, have been reported on SWCNT dispersed in liquids⁵⁻⁷. In these cases the scattering intensity has been shown to follow a power law as $I(q) \propto q^{-\alpha}$ where $q = 4\pi\sin(2\theta)/\lambda$ is the scattering vector being 2θ the scattering angle and λ the wave length of the radiation used. Values of $\alpha \approx 2-2.5$ were found while if isolated SWCNTs units were the scatterers then a value of $\alpha \approx 1$ would

be expected⁵. The higher values were interpreted as due to the fact that SWCNT aggregates forming structures of fractal nature⁵⁻⁸. Accordingly, small-angle scattering techniques can be considered as a non destructive method to probe aggregation in nanocomposites. Similar procedure have been recently applied to nanocomposites of SWCNT in a thermoset polymer⁹ and of multi wall carbon nanotubes (MWCNT) in a thermoplastic polymer (polyamide 6, PA6)¹⁰. In the case of PA6 the samples exhibited a strong correlation peak due to the long spacing of PA6 which is a semicrystalline polymer. Therefore the subtraction of the polymer scattering may introduce additional uncertainty to estimate the sole contribution of the carbon nanotubes. The aim of this study is to provide information, by means of small-angle X-ray scattering, about the aggregation level of SWCNT dispersed in a thermoplastic semicrystalline polymer in its molten state in order to avoid the influence of the correlation peak associated to its semicrystalline nature.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Materials and Sample preparation

Nanocomposites based on poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) ((Rhodia S80 from RhodiaSter, $M_v=45000$ g/mol) and single-wall carbon nanotubes (CNI Technology Co., Texas, USA, synthesized by using the HiPco method) several microns length and about 1.4 nm in diameter, as revealed by Raman spectroscopy, were prepared by mixing SWCNT with the polymer melt. Selected amounts of SWCNT were added to the polymer melt (280 °C) while stirring at 100 rpm the mixture during about 5 minutes at maximum torque of 3.6 Nm. An internal mixer Microconpounder from DACA instruments (Goleta CA93116) was used. . Different nanocomposites with SWCNT weight concentration between 0 and 5 % were obtained. The internal mixer method was selected instead of the solution mixing in order to mimic the foreseeable industrial

processing which could follow the manufacturing of SWCNT-polymer nanocomposites. Films of the nanocomposites with thicknesses of about 300 μm were prepared by mould pressing at 280 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

2.2. Techniques

Small-angle X-ray scattering

Small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) experiments were performed in the Soft Condensed Matter beam-line A2 at HASYLAB in the synchrotron facility (DESY in Hamburg, Germany). The sample cell was incorporated to a vacuum chamber (10^{-2} torr) specially designed to perform X-ray scattering measurements with synchrotron radiation. A wavelength $\lambda=0.15\text{nm}$ was used for X-ray diffraction study. A rat tendon tail was used for calibration. Each frame was collected during 60 s and later corrected for air background and primary beam intensity fluctuations during experiment.

3. Results and Discussion

Fig.1a shows the scattered intensity at $T=290^{\circ}\text{C}$ as a function of the scattering vector q for the PET polymer matrix and for the composites whose SWCNT weight concentration has been labelled on the right. The temperature is well above the melting point of the crystalline phase of PET and it was chosen in order to avoid the contribution to the SAXS signal of the characteristic long-spacing of semicrystalline PET¹¹. The data are presented in a double logarithmic scale in order to emphasize the power law followed by the scattered intensity. The scattered intensities at lower q -values increase with the SWCNT concentration being more than one order of magnitude higher for the nanocomposite with 5 % of SWCNT than for the polymer matrix. This fact implies an increase of the scatterer size as the intensity at $q \rightarrow 0$ scales with the molecular weight⁶. The straight lines represent the linear fits of the experimental data to a law of the type $\text{Log}_{10}(I)=A - \alpha\text{Log}_{10}(q)$, being α the slope of the straight line. Fig.1b

represents the experimental data after subtraction of the contribution from the scattering of the molten polymer matrix. The different slopes are represented in fig. 2 as a function of the weight concentration of SWCNT. Additionally the slopes resulting from experimental data of fig.1 after subtracting the scattering contribution of molten polymer matrix are also displayed. Both set of data in fig. 2 exhibit a clear “percolative” dependence of the slope with the nanoadditive concentration. The initial value of 2.7 for the polymer matrix suddenly decreases for concentrations of SWCNTs higher than about 0.1 % and then levels off towards a limiting value of ≈ 2.1 . Similarly to what it has been reported for dispersion of SWCNTs in liquids^{5,6}, the results of fig.1 indicate the absence of the clear signature of individual rod-like scatters which would produce slope values of $\alpha=1$. On the contrary the observed slopes in the region of 2.1 for the nanocomposites can be interpreted as due the scattering of a mass fractal consisting on SWCNT agglomerates. Fractal objects are made from self-similar motifs over different ranges of length scales⁸. In accordance with the general view of scattering from fractals⁸ and with recent experiments on SWCNT suspensions⁵⁻⁷ the slopes observed for the SWCNT nanocomposites may correspond to branched rope-like structures of bundled carbon nanotubes. The higher slope of $\alpha=2.7$ observed for the polymer matrix can also be interpreted as due to a polymer chain aggregate of different nature as those of SWCNTs. Fig. 3 shows a micrography of the original SWCNTs. It is clear that the nanoadditive consists of a branched network formed by the characteristic ropes of nanotubes. Upon mixing in the molten polymer matrix the shear forces are not enough to break the rope morphology. Therefore the resulting morphology retains an aggregate morphology and it is responsible for the slopes, different from $\alpha=1$, observed in the SAXS experiments. In principle, this is expected considering that SAXS experiments performed in SWCNT suspensions vigorously treated by sonication⁶ and or even in

suspensions of functionalized SWCNT⁵ show no signature of isolated nanotubes. Only for certain surfactants and under dilute conditions small angle neutron scattering revealed the existence of isolated nanotubes in the liquid suspension⁷. As mentioned by some authors⁶ the existence of morphology of branched agglomerates for SWCNTs has significant impact on the mechanical properties of the nanocomposite material due to the absence of the reinforcing effect expected for single SWCNTs. However, as far as the electrical properties are concerned, the situation could be quite the opposite. It is known for long time¹², in the field of carbon-black polymer composites, that the level of aggregation favours the formation of conducting network by decreasing the percolation threshold^{12,13}. As a matter of fact, all the investigated nanocomposites here present electrical conductivity values well above the percolation threshold. Therefore probably a compromise must be reached in order to optimize either the mechanical or the electrical properties of the nanocomposite material. In this respect small angle X-ray scattering is shown to be a valuable tool to assess the level of nanotube dispersion achieved in polymer-SWCNT nanocomposites.

4. Conclusions

By means of small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) we have studied the level of aggregation for different concentrations of SWCNT dispersed in molten poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET). The scattered intensity follows a power law concentration which can be interpreted as due to the presence of branched rope-like structures of bundled nanotubes.

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Legends to the figures

Fig.1. (a) Double logarithmic scale representation of the SAXS intensity at 290 °C as a function of the scattering vector q for a series of SWCNT dispersions in molten PET with SWCNT concentrations (in weight %) labelled on the right side. The straight lines are the best linear fits to the experimental data. (b) Similar plot for the data after subtraction of the scattering from the molten polymer matrix.

Fig.2. (●) Slopes of the straight lines fitted to plots of fig.1 as a function of the SWCNT concentrations. (■) Slopes of the scattering curves after subtraction of the scattering of the polymer matrix. The continuous line is a guide for the eye.

Fig.3. Scanning electron micrograph (SEM) of the SWCNT used in the nanocomposite preparation

Fig.1

Fig.2

Fig.3